

Cloud Deep Networks for Hyperspectral Image Analysis

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Abstract—Advances in remote sensing hardware have led to a significantly increased capability for high quality data acquisition, which allows the collection of remotely sensed images with very high spatial, spectral and radiometric resolution. This trend calls for the development of new techniques to enhance the way such unprecedented volumes of data are stored, processed and analyzed. An important approach to deal with massive volumes of information is data compression, related to how data are compressed before their storage or transmission. For instance, hyperspectral images (HSIs) are characterized by hundreds of spectral bands. In this sense, high performance (HPC) and high throughput (HTC) computing offer interesting alternatives. Particularly, distributed solutions based on cloud computing can manage and store huge amounts of data in fault-tolerant environments, by interconnecting distributed computing nodes so that no specialized hardware is needed. This strategy greatly reduces the processing costs, making the processing of high volumes of remotely sensed data a natural and even cheap solution. In this paper, we present a new cloud-based technique for spectral analysis and compression of HSIs. Specifically, we develop a cloud implementation of a popular deep neural network for non-linear data compression, known as auto-encoder (AE). Apache Spark serves as the backbone of our cloud computing environment by connecting the available processing nodes using a master-slave architecture. Our newly developed approach has been tested using two widely available HSI datasets. Experimental results indicate that cloud computing architectures offer an adequate solution for managing big remotely sensed data sets.

Index Terms—High performance computing (HPC), high throughput computing (HTC), cloud computing, hyperspectral

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I. INTRODUCTION

EARTH Observation (EO) has evolved dramatically in the last decades due to the technological advances incorporated into remote sensing instruments in the optical and microwave domains [1]. With their hundreds of contiguous and narrow channels within the visible, near-infrared and short-wave infrared spectral ranges, hyperspectral images (HSIs) have been used for the retrieval of bio-, geo-chemical and physical parameters that characterize the surface of the earth. These data are now used in a wide-range of applications, aimed at monitoring and implementing new policies in the domain of agriculture, geology, assessment of environmental resources, urban planning, military/defense, disaster management, etc. [2], [3], [4].

Most of the developments carried out over the last decades in the field of imaging spectroscopy have been achieved via spectrometers on board airborne platforms. For instance, the Airborne Visible/Infrared Imaging Spectrometer (AVIRIS) [5] has been dedicated to remote sensing of the earth in a large number of experiments and field campaigns since the late 1980s. Other examples of airborne missions include the European Space Agency (ESA)'s Airborne Prism Experiment (APEX) (2011-2016) [6], or the Compact Airborne Spectrographic Imager (CASI) [7] (1989-today), among many others.

The vast amount of data collected by airborne platforms has paved the way for EO satellite hyperspectral missions. The Hyperion instrument on-board NASA's Earth Observing One (EO-1) spacecraft (2000-2017) [8] and the Compact High Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (CHRIS) on ESA's Proba-1 microsatellite [9] (2001-today) have been to of the main sources of space-based HSI data in the last decades. Currently, there are several HSI missions under development, including the Environmental Mapping and Analysis Program (EnMAP) [10], the Prototype Research Instruments and Space Mission technology Advancement (PRISMA) [11], among others.

The adoption of an open and free data policy by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) [12] and, more recently, by ESA's Copernicus initiative (the largest single EO program) [13] is now producing an unprecedented amount of data to the research community. Even though the Copernicus space component (i.e., the Sentinels) have not included a hyperspectral instrument yet (Sentinel-10 is a HSI mission expected to be operational around 2025-2030), it has been shown

that the vast amount of open data currently available calls for re-definition of the challenges within the entire HSI life cycle (i.e., data acquisition, processing and application phases). It is not by coincidence that remote sensing data are now described under the *big data* terminology, with characteristics such as volume (increasing scale of acquired/archived data), velocity (rapidly growing data generation rate, real-time processing needs), variety (data acquired from multiple sources), veracity (data uncertainty/accuracy), and value (extracted information) [14], [15].

In this context, traditional processing methods such as desktop approaches (i.e., MATLAB, R, SAS, ENVI, etc.) offer limited capabilities when dealing with such large amounts of data, especially regarding the velocity component (i.e., the demand for real-time applications). Despite modern desktop computers and laptops are becoming increasingly more powerful, with multi-core and many-core capabilities including graphics processing units (GPUs), the limitations in terms of memory and core availability currently limit the processing of large HSI data archives. Therefore, the use of highly scalable parallel/distributed architectures (such as GPUs, clusters [16], grids [17] or clouds [18], [19]) is a mandatory solution to improve the access to and the analysis of such great amount of complex data, in order to provide decision-makers with clear, timely, and useful information [20], [21]. In this context, parallel and distributed computing approaches can be categorized into high performance computing (HPC) or high throughput computing (HTC) solutions. Contrary to an HPC system [22] (generally, a supercomputer that includes a massive number of processors connected through a fast dedicated network, i.e. a cluster), an HTC system (for instance a grid) is more focused on the execution of independent and sequential jobs that can be individually scheduled on many different computing resources, regardless of how fast an individual job can be completed. Cloud computing is the natural evolution of grid computing, adopting its backbone and infrastructure [19] but delivering computing resources *as a service* over the network connection [23]. In other words, the cloud moves desktop and laptop computing (via the Internet) to a service-oriented platform using large remote server clusters, and massive storage to data centres. In this scenario, computing relies on sharing a pool of physical and/or virtual resources, rather than on deploying local or personal hardware and software. The process of virtualization has enabled the cost-effectiveness and simplicity of cloud computing solutions [24] (i.e., it exempts users from the need to purchase and maintain complex computing hardware) such as IaaS (infrastructure as a service), PaaS (platform as a service), or SaaS (software as a service). Several cloud computing resources are currently available commercially, on a *pay as you go* model from providers such as Amazon Web Services (AWS) [25], Microsoft Azure [26], and Google's Compute Engine [27].

Cloud computing infrastructures can rely on several computing frameworks that support the processing of large data sets in a distributed environment. For example, the MapReduce model [28] is the basis of a large number of open-source implementations. The most popular ones are Apache Hadoop [29] and its variant, Apache Spark [30] (an in-memory computing

framework). Despite the recent advances in cloud computing technology, not enough efforts have been devoted to exploiting cloud computing infrastructures for the processing of HSI data. However, cloud computing offers a natural solution for the processing of large HSI databases, as well as an evolution of previously developed techniques for other kinds of computing platforms, mainly due to the capacity of cloud computing to provide internet-scale, service-oriented computing [31], [32], [33].

In this work, we focus on the problem of how to develop scalable data analysis and compression techniques [34], [35], [4], [36] with the goal of facilitating the management of remotely sensed HSI data. In this sense, deep learning (DL) methods based on neural network architectures have gained significant interest in HSI image analysis and processing [37] due to the flexibility of their architectures, their learning models and the amount of tasks they can perform [38]. As a result, dimensionality reduction (DR) of HSIs is a fundamental pre-processing step that is applied before many data transfer, store and processing operations. On the one hand, when HSI data are efficiently compressed, they can be handled more efficiently on-board satellite platforms with limited storage and downlink bandwidth. On the other hand, since HSI data lives primarily in a subspace [39], a few informative features can be extracted from the hundreds of highly correlated spectral bands that comprise HSI data [40] without significantly affecting the data quality (lossy compression of HSIs can still retain informative data for subsequent processing steps).

Specifically, this paper develops a new cloud implementation of HSI data compression based on neural networks. As in [41], we adopt the Apache Spark framework as well as a map-reduce methodology [24] to carry out our implementation. In addition, we address the DR problem using a non-linear deep auto-encoder (AE) neural network instead of the standard linear principal component analysis (PCA) algorithm. In fact, we implement a new scalable cloud implementation of the neural model proposed by [42], which is characterized by its flexibility to perform different tasks beyond DR, such as classification [42] or spectral unmixing [43], so the proposed methodology can be easily adapted to perform different tasks. Focusing on DR, the performance of our newly proposed cloud-based AE is validated using two widely available and known HSI data sets. Our experimental results show that the proposed implementation can effectively exploit cloud computing technology to efficiently perform non-linear compression of large HSI data sets, while accelerating significantly the processing time in a distributed environment.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II provides an overview of the theoretical and operational details of the considered AE neural network for HSI data compression, and the considered optimization method. Section III presents our cloud-distributed AE network for HSI data compression, describing the details of the network configuration and the distributed implementation. Section IV evaluates the performance of the proposed approach using two widely available HSI data sets, taking into account the quality of the compression and signal reconstruction, and also the computational efficiency of the implementation in a real

cloud environment. Finally, section V concludes the work, summarizing the obtained results and suggesting some future research directions.

II. BACKGROUND

HSI data are characterized by their intrinsically complex spectral characteristics, where samples of the same class exhibit high variability due to data acquisition factors or atmospheric and lighting interferers. DR and feature extraction (FE) methods are fundamental tools for the extraction of discriminative features that reduce the intra-class variability and inter-class similarity [44] present in HSI data sets. Furthermore, by reducing the high spectral dimensionality of HSIs, these methods are able to alleviate the *curse of dimensionality* [45], which makes HSI data difficult to interpret by supervised classifiers due to the Hughes phenomenon [46].

Several methods have been developed to perform DR and FE from HSIs. For instance, Kang *et al.* proposed in [47] a decolorization method to reduce the spectral dimensionality of HSI scenes, preserving most of the information contained in them. In [48], they adopted DR methods with data filtering, implementing image fusion and recursive filtering (IFRF) to preserve the physical meaning of the spectral pixels. In [49], they implemented morphological attribute thinning and thickening (attribute filtering) to perform advanced feature extraction for HSI interpretation. Other interesting DR and FE methods are the independent component analysis (ICA) [50], [51] or the maximum noise fraction (MNF) [52], [53], being PCA [54], [55], [56] one of the most widely used methods for FE purposes. This unsupervised, linear algorithm reduces the original high-dimensional and correlated feature space to a lower-dimensional space of uncorrelated factors (also called principal components or PCs) by applying an orthogonal transformation through a projection matrix, which makes it a simple yet efficient algorithm. However, PCA is restricted to a linear map-projection and is not able to learn non-linear transformations. In this context, auto-associative¹ neural networks such as AEs [57] offer a more flexible architecture for FE and DR purposes, managing the non-linearities of the data through an architecture made up of stacked layers and non-linear activation functions (called stacked AE or SAE) that can provide more detailed data representations from the original input image (one per layer), which can be easily reused by other HSI processing methods [42], [43].

A. Auto-encoder (AE) Neural Network

Let us consider a HSI data cube $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1 \times n_2 \times n_{bands}}$, where $n_1 \times n_2$ are the spatial dimensions and n_{bands} is the number of spectral bands. \mathbf{X} is traditionally observed by pixel-based algorithms as a collection of $n_1 \times n_2$ spectral samples, where each $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{bands}} = [x_{i,1}, x_{i,2}, \dots, x_{i,n_{bands}}]$ contains the spectral signature of the observed surface material. In this sense, the goal of DR methods is to obtain, for each \mathbf{x}_i , a vector $\mathbf{c}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{new}}$ that captures the most

¹Auto-associative networks are those whose inputs can be inferred from the outputs. The proposed implementation of a non-linear autoencoder belongs to this kind of networks.

Fig. 1. Graphic representation of a traditional auto-encoder for spectral compression and restoration of hyperspectral images.

representative information of \mathbf{x}_i in a lower feature-space, being $n_{new} \ll n_{bands}$. To achieve this goal, the SAE applies an unsupervised symmetrical deep neural network to encode the data in a lower-dimensional latent space, performing a traditional embedding, and then decoding it to the original space through a reconstruction stage. In fact, the SAE can be interpreted as a mirrored net, where three main parts can be identified (as shown in Fig. 1): i) the encoder or mapping layers, ii) the middle or bottleneck layer, and iii) the decoder or demapping layers. Based on the traditional multilayer perceptron (MLP), the l -th layer defined in the SAE performs an affine transformation between the input data $\mathbf{x}_i^{(l)}$ and its set of weights $\mathbf{W}^{(l)}$ and biases $b^{(l)}$, as Eq. (1) indicates:

$$\mathbf{x}_i^{(l+1)} = \mathcal{H} \left(\mathbf{x}_i^{(l)} \cdot \mathbf{W}^{(l)} + b^{(l)} \right), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_i^{(l+1)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n^{(l+)}}$ is an abstract representation (or feature representation) of the original input data \mathbf{x}_i in the feature space obtained by the $n^{(l)}$ neurons that compose the l -th layer, where the output of the k -th neuron is obtained as the dot product between the $n^{(l-1)}$ outputs of the previous layer and its weights, passed through an activation function that is usually implemented by the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) [58], i.e. $\mathcal{H}(x) = \max(0, x)$. Finally, the k -th feature in $\mathbf{x}_i^{(l+1)}$ can be obtained as:

$$x_{i,k}^{(l+1)} = \mathcal{H} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{n^{(l-1)}} \left(x_{i,j}^{(l)} \cdot w_{k,j}^{(l)} \right) + b^{(l)} \right). \quad (2)$$

With this in mind, the SAE applies two main processing steps to each input sample \mathbf{x}_i . The first one, known as *coding stage*, performs the embedding of the data, mapping it from $\mathbb{R}^{n_{bands}}$ space to $\mathbb{R}^{n_{new}}$ latent space. That is, the $n_{encoder}$ layers of the encoder map their input data to a projected representation following Eqs. (1) and (2), until reaching the bottleneck layer. As a result, the bottleneck layer contains the projection of each $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{bands}}$ in its latent space,

defined by its n_{new} neurons, $\mathbf{c}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{new}}$. As a result, the SAE allows to generate compressed ($n_{new} < n_{bands}$), extended ($n_{new} > n_{bands}$) or even equally ($n_{new} = n_{bands}$) dimensional representations, depending on the final dimension of the code vector \mathbf{c}_i .

The second stage performs the opposite operation, i.e. the *decoding*, where the network tries to recover the original information, obtaining an approximate reconstruction of the original input vector [59]. In this case, the $n_{decoder}$ layers of the decoder demap the code vector \mathbf{c}_i until reaching the output layer, where a reconstructed sample \mathbf{x}'_i is obtained. Eq. (3) gives an overview of the encoding-decoding process followed by the SAE:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{c}_i &\leftarrow \text{For } l \text{ in } n_{encoder}: \mathbf{x}_i^{(l+1)} = \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}_i^{(l)} \cdot \mathbf{W}^{(l)} + b^{(l)}) \\ \mathbf{x}'_i &\leftarrow \text{For } ll \text{ in } n_{decoder}: \mathbf{c}_i^{(ll+1)} = \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{c}_i^{(ll)} \cdot \mathbf{W}^{(ll)} + b^{(ll)}) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In order to obtain a lower-dimensional (but more discriminative) representation of the input data, the network parameters are iteratively adjusted in unsupervised fashion, where the optimizer minimizes the reconstruction error between the input data at the encoding stage, \mathbf{x}_i , and its reconstruction at the end of the decoding stage, \mathbf{x}'_i . This error function, given by Eq. (4), is usually implemented in the form of a mean squared error (MSE):

$$E(\mathbf{X}) = \min \|\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{X}'\|_2 = \min \sum_{i=1}^{n_1 \cdot n_2} \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}'_i\|_2. \quad (4)$$

B. Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno (BFGS) Algorithm

After describing the operational procedure of SAEs, it is now important to observe the network optimization process. As any artificial neural network with back-propagation, the optimizer tries to find the set of parameters (synaptic weights and biases) that, for a given network architecture, minimize the error function $E(\mathbf{X})$ defined by Eq. (4). This function evaluates how well the neural network fits the dataset \mathbf{X} , and depends on the adaptative and learnable parameters of the network, that can be denoted as \mathcal{W} , so $E(\mathbf{X}, \mathcal{W})$. As $E(\mathbf{X}, \mathcal{W})$ is non-linear, its optimization must be carried out iteratively, reducing its value until an adequate stopping criterion is reached. In this sense, standard optimizers back-propagate the error signal through the network architecture calculating, for each learnable parameter, the gradient of the error, i.e. the direction and displacement that the parameter must undergo in order to minimize the final error (also interpreted as the importance of that parameter when obtaining the final error). Mathematically, the updating of \mathcal{W} in the t -th epoch can be calculated by Eq. (5):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{W}_{t+1} &= \mathcal{W}_t + \Delta\mathcal{W}, \\ \text{being } \Delta\mathcal{W} &= \mu_t \cdot \mathbf{p}_t, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where μ_t and \mathbf{p}_t are the learning rate (a positive scalar) and the descent search direction, respectively [60]. The main goal of any optimizer is to obtain the correct \mathbf{p}_t in order to descend properly in the error function until the minimum is reached.

As opposed to standard optimizers, traditional Newton-based methods determine the descent direction \mathbf{p}_t using the second derivative information contained into the Hessian matrix, rather than just the gradient information, thus stabilizing the process:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{H}_t \cdot \mathbf{p}_t &= -\nabla E(\mathbf{X}, \mathcal{W}_t) \\ \mathbf{p}_t &= -\mathbf{H}_t^{-1} \cdot \nabla E(\mathbf{X}, \mathcal{W}_t) \\ \mathcal{W}_{t+1} &= \mathcal{W}_t - \mu_t \cdot \mathbf{H}_t^{-1} \cdot \nabla E(\mathbf{X}, \mathcal{W}_t), \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $\nabla E(\mathbf{X}, \mathcal{W}_t)$ is the gradient of the error function evaluated with the network's parameters at the t -th epoch, \mathcal{W}_t , and \mathbf{H}_t and \mathbf{H}_t^{-1} are respectively the Hessian matrix and its inverse, obtained at the t -th epoch. However, these methods obtain the Hessian matrix and its inverse at each epoch, which is quite expensive to compute, requiring a large amount of memory. Instead of that, the *Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno* (BFGS) method [61] performs an estimation of how the Hessian matrix has changed in each epoch, obtaining an approximation (instead of the full matrix) that is improved every epoch. In fact, as any algorithm of the family of multivariate minimization quasi-newton methods, the BFGS algorithm modifies the last expression of Eq. (6) as follows:

$$\mathcal{W}_{t+1} = \mathcal{W}_t - \mu_t \cdot \mathbf{G}_t \cdot \nabla E(\mathbf{X}, \mathcal{W}_t), \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{G}_t is the inverse Hessian approximation matrix (usually, when $t = 0$ the initial approximation matrix is the identity matrix, $\mathbf{G}_0 = \mathbf{I}$). This \mathbf{G}_t is updated at each epoch by means of an update matrix:

$$\mathbf{G}_{t+1} = \mathbf{G}_t + \mathbf{U}_t. \quad (8)$$

However, such update needs to comply with the quasi-Newton condition, which is described below. Assuming that $E(\mathbf{X}, \mathcal{W})$ is continuous for \mathcal{W}_t and \mathcal{W}_{t+1} (with gradients $\mathbf{g}_t = \nabla E(\mathbf{X}, \mathcal{W}_t)$ and $\mathbf{g}_{t+1} = \nabla E(\mathbf{X}, \mathcal{W}_{t+1})$, respectively) and the Hessian \mathbf{H} is constant, then Eq. (9) is satisfied:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{q}_t &\equiv \mathbf{g}_{t+1} - \mathbf{g}_t \text{ and } \mathbf{p}_t \equiv \mathcal{W}_{t+1} - \mathcal{W}_t \\ \text{Secant condition on the Hessian: } &\mathbf{q}_t = \mathbf{H} \cdot \mathbf{p}_t \\ \text{Secant condition on the inverse: } &\mathbf{H}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{q}_t = \mathbf{p}_t \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Since $\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{H}^{-1}$, the last expression in Eq. (9) can be modified to $\mathbf{G} \cdot \mathbf{q}_t = \mathbf{p}_t$, so the approximation matrix \mathbf{G} can be obtained (at each epoch t) as a combination of the linearly independent directions and their respective gradients. Following the Davidon, Fletcher and Powell (DFP) rank 2 formula [62], \mathbf{G} can be updated using Eq. (10):

$$\mathbf{G}_{t+1} = \mathbf{G}_t + \frac{\mathbf{p}_t \cdot \mathbf{p}_t^\top}{\mathbf{p}_t^\top \cdot \mathbf{q}_t} - \mathbf{G}_t \cdot \frac{\mathbf{q}_t \cdot \mathbf{q}_t^\top}{\mathbf{q}_t^\top \cdot \mathbf{G}_t \cdot \mathbf{q}_t} \cdot \mathbf{G}_t. \quad (10)$$

Finally, the BFGS method updates its approximation matrix by computing the complementary formula of the DFP method, changing \mathbf{G} by \mathbf{H} and \mathbf{p}_t by \mathbf{q}_t , so Eq. (10) is finally modified as follows:

$$\mathbf{H}_{t+1} = \mathbf{H}_t + \frac{\mathbf{q}_t \cdot \mathbf{q}_t^\top}{\mathbf{q}_t^\top \cdot \mathbf{p}_t} - \mathbf{H}_t \cdot \frac{\mathbf{p}_t \cdot \mathbf{p}_t^\top}{\mathbf{p}_t^\top \cdot \mathbf{H}_t \cdot \mathbf{p}_t} \cdot \mathbf{H}_t. \quad (11)$$

As the BFGS method intends to compute the inverse of \mathbf{H} and $\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{H}^{-1}$, it inverts Eq. (11) to analytically obtain the final update of the approximation matrix:

$$\mathbf{G}_{t+1} = \mathbf{G}_t + \left(1 + \frac{\mathbf{q}_t^\top \cdot \mathbf{G}_t \cdot \mathbf{q}_t}{\mathbf{q}_t^\top \cdot \mathbf{p}_t} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{\mathbf{p}_t \cdot \mathbf{p}_t^\top}{\mathbf{p}_t^\top \cdot \mathbf{q}_t} \right) - \frac{\mathbf{p}_t \cdot \mathbf{q}_t^\top \cdot \mathbf{G}_t + \mathbf{G}_t \cdot \mathbf{q}_t \cdot \mathbf{p}_t^\top}{\mathbf{q}_t^\top \cdot \mathbf{p}_t} \quad (12)$$

Algorithm 1 Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno Algorithm

- 1: **procedure** BFGS(\mathcal{W}_t : current parameters of the neural network, $E(\mathbf{X}, \mathcal{W})$: Error function, \mathbf{G}_t : current approximation to the Hessian)
 - 2: $\mathbf{g}_t = \nabla E(\mathbf{X}, \mathcal{W}_t)$
 - 3: $\mathbf{p}_t = -\mathbf{G}_t \cdot \mathbf{g}_t$
 - 4: $\mathcal{W}_{t+1} = \mathcal{W}_t + \mu_t \cdot \mathbf{p}_t$ $\triangleright \mu_t$ by linear search
 - 5: $\mathbf{g}_{t+1} = \nabla E(\mathbf{X}, \mathcal{W}_{t+1})$
 - 6: $\mathbf{q}_t = \mathbf{g}_{t+1} - \mathbf{g}_t$
 - 7: $\mathbf{p}_t = \mathcal{W}_{t+1} - \mathcal{W}_t$
 - 8: $\mathbf{A} = \left(1 + \frac{\mathbf{q}_t^\top \cdot \mathbf{G}_t \cdot \mathbf{q}_t}{\mathbf{q}_t^\top \cdot \mathbf{p}_t} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{\mathbf{p}_t \cdot \mathbf{p}_t^\top}{\mathbf{p}_t^\top \cdot \mathbf{q}_t} \right)$
 - 9: $\mathbf{B} = \frac{\mathbf{p}_t \cdot \mathbf{q}_t^\top \cdot \mathbf{G}_t + \mathbf{G}_t \cdot \mathbf{q}_t \cdot \mathbf{p}_t^\top}{\mathbf{q}_t^\top \cdot \mathbf{p}_t}$
 - 10: $\mathbf{G}_{t+1} = \mathbf{G}_t + \mathbf{A} - \mathbf{B}$
 - return** $\mathcal{W}_{t+1}, \mathbf{G}_{t+1}$
 - 11: **end procedure**
-

Algorithm 1 provides a general overview of how the BFGS method works in one epoch. As shown in line 4 of Algorithm 1, as opposed to most optimization algorithms, the learning rate is inferred by performing a linear search instead of using an input parameter. A weakness of BFGS is that it requires the computation of the gradient on the full dataset, consuming a large amount of memory to properly run the optimization. Taking into account the dimensionality of HSIs, we can conclude that this method is not able to scale with the number of samples [63]. In order to overcome this limitation, and with the aim of speeding up the computation of both the forward (affine transformations) and backward (optimizer) steps of the AE for DR of HSIs, in the following section we develop a distributed solution for cloud computing environments.

III. PROPOSED IMPLEMENTATION

A. Distributed Framework

We have developed a completely new distributed AE for HSI data analysis² that follows the diagram depicted in Fig. 2, where it is shown that the proposed cloud-based neural model has been implemented as a master-slave, multi-node environment. In this context, two problems have been specifically addressed in this work: i) the computing engine, and ii) the distributed programming model over the cloud architecture. Regarding the first problem, our distributed implementation of the network model is run on top of a standalone Spark cluster, due to its capacity to provide fast processing of large data volumes on distributed platforms, in addition to fault-tolerance. Furthermore, the Spark cluster is characterized

Fig. 2. Diagram summarizing the overall framework of the proposed cloud implementation, where the master node takes the HSI data and partitions it between the different workers nodes, which apply the tasks extracted from the graph of transformations, executing the forward and backward steps over their data. The obtained gradients are collected and pooled by the master node, which transmits the final gradient to the neural models stored by each worker node.

by a master-slave architecture, which makes it very flexible. Specifically, a Spark cluster is formed by a master node, which manages how the resources are used and distributed in the cluster by hosting a Java virtual machine (JVM) driver, and the scheduler, which distributes the tasks between the execution nodes, and N worker nodes (which can be more than one per node) that execute the program tasks by creating a Java distributed agent, called executor (where tasks are computed), and store the data partitions (see Fig. 3).

In relation to the second point, the adopted programming model to perform the implementation of the distributed AE is based on organizing the original HSI data in tuples or key/value pairs, in order to apply the *MapReduce* model [41], which divides the data processing task into two distributed operations: i) *mapping*, which processes a set of data-tuples, generating intermediate key-value pairs, and ii) *reduction*, which gathers all the intermediate pairs obtained by the mapping to generate the final result. In order to achieve this behavior, data information in Spark is abstracted and encapsulated into a fault-tolerant data structure called *Resilient Distributed Dataset* (RDD). These RDDs are organized as distributed collections of data, which are scattered by Spark across the worker nodes when they are needed on the successive computations, being persisted on the memory of the nodes or on the disk. This architecture allows for the parallelization of the executions, achieved by performing *MapReduce* tasks over the RDDs on the nodes. Moreover, two basic operations can be performed on a RDD: i) the so-called *transformations*, which are based on applying an operation to every row on a partition, resulting in another RDD, and ii) *actions*, which retrieve a value or a set of values that can be both RDD data or the result of an operation where some RDD data are involved. Operations are queued until an action is called; the needed transformations are placed into a dependency graph, where each node is a job stage, following a lazy execution paradigm. This means that operations are not performed until they are really needed, avoiding the repetition of a single operation

²Code available on: <https://github.com/jgallardst/cloud-nn-hsi>

more than once.

In order to enable a simple and easy mechanism for managing large data sets, the Spark environment provides another level of abstraction that uses the concept of *Dataframe*. These Dataframes allow data to be organized on named columns, being easier to manipulate (as in relational tables, columns can be accessed by the column name instead of by the index). With this in mind, the Spark standalone cluster functionality can be summarized as follows:

- 1) The master node (also called driver node) creates and manages the Spark driver (see Fig. 3), a Java process that contains the SparkContext of the application.
- 2) The driver context performs the data partitioning and parallelization between the worker nodes, assigning to each one a number of partitions, which depends on two main aspects: the block size and the way the data are stacked. Also, the driver creates the executors on the worker nodes, which store data partitions on the worker node and perform tasks on them.
- 3) When an action is called, a job is launched and the master coordinates how the associated tasks are distributed into the different executors. In order to reduce the data exchanging time, the Spark driver attempts to perform “smart” task allocations, so that there are more possibilities to assign a task to the executor, located in the worker where the data partition used by the task to perform the operation has been allocated.
- 4) When all the tasks on a given stage are finished, the Scheduler allocates another stage of the job (if it was a transformation), or retrieves the final output (if it was an action).

Algorithm 2 shows a general overview of how our algorithm is pipelined in the considered Spark cluster.

Algorithm 2 Iterative Process

```

1: procedure SPARK FLOW
2:   PartitionedData ← Spark.parallelizeData()
3:   t ← 0
4:   while t < niterations do
5:     broadcastOutputData()
6:     foreach partition ∈ PartitionedData do
7:       PartitionedData.applyTask()
8:     end for
9:     retrieveOutputData()
10:    t ← t + 1
11:  end while
12: end procedure

```

B. Cloud Autoencoder Pipeline Implementation: Training and Optimization Process

This section describes in detail the full distributed training process, from the parallelization of HSI data across nodes to the intrinsic logic of each training step, explaining the benefits of our distributed training algorithm. Fig. 4 gives a general overview of the full data pipeline developed in this work.

Fig. 3. Graphic representation of a generic Spark cluster, which is composed by one client node and N worker nodes, where in each node several executor Java virtual machines are running in parallel over several data partitions.

In the beginning, the original 3-dimensional HSI data cube $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1 \times n_2 \times n_{bands}}$, where $n_1 \times n_2$ are the spatial dimensions (height and width) and n_{bands} is the spectral dimension given by the number of spectral channels, is reshaped into a HSI matrix $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{pixels} \times n_{bands}}$, where $n_{pixels} = n_1 \times n_2$, i.e. each row collects a full spectral pixel, being each column the corresponding value in the spectral band. This matrix \mathbf{X} is read by the Spark Driver, which collects the original HSI data and partitions it into P smaller subsets that are delivered to the worker nodes in parallel. These workers store the obtained partitions on their local disks. In this sense, each data partition composes a RDD.

It must be noted that complex neural network topologies derive on greedy RAM memory usage on the driver node. Since Spark transformations apply an operation to every row of the RDD, the fewer the number of rows, the fewer the number of operations that must be carried out. In order to improve the computation of the distributed model, a *blocksize* (BS) hyperparameter is provided, with the aim of indicating how many pixels should be stacked into a single row in order to compute them together. With this observation in mind, the p -th data partition (with $p = 1, \dots, P$) can be seen as a 2-dimensional matrix ${}^{(p)}\mathbf{D} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{rows} \times (BS \cdot n_{bands})}$ composed by n_{rows} rows, where each one stores BS concatenated spectral pixels, i.e. ${}^{(p)}\mathbf{d}_j \in \mathbb{R}^{(BS \cdot n_{bands})} = [\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_{i+1}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{i+BS}]$. In the end, each data partition ${}^{(p)}\mathbf{D}$ stores $BS \cdot n_{rows}$ pixels. The resulting partitions are then distributed across the worker nodes. Such distribution allows the executors, located in each worker node, to apply the subsequent tasks to those partitions that each worker receives.

After distributing the data into RDDs, a distributed data analysis process begins prior to the application of neural network-based processing. In the first step, the data contained in each partition ${}^{(p)}\mathbf{D}$ are scaled in a distributed way, taking advantage of the cloud architecture and the available paral-

Fig. 4. Data pipeline of our distributed auto-encoder, where the input HSI cube is first reshaped into a matrix and then split into several partitions allocated into the Spark worker nodes, composed by several rows where each one contains BS spectral pixels. These data partitions are then duplicated in order to obtain the input network data and the corresponding output network data. The AE is then executed and, for each iteration t , the gradients are collected by the Spark driver, which calculates the final gradient and performs the optimization with the L-BFGS algorithm. The updated weights are finally broadcasted to each neural model contained in the cluster.

lization of resources. In this sense, each partition's row $(p)\mathbf{d}_j$ (and, internally, each pixel contained within) is transformed based on the global maximum and minimum features (\mathbf{x}_{max} and \mathbf{x}_{min}) of the whole image \mathbf{X} , and the column local maximum and minimum features $(p)\mathbf{d}_{max}$ and $(p)\mathbf{d}_{min}$, of the p -th partition where the data are allocated:

$$\begin{aligned} (p)\hat{\mathbf{d}}_j &= \frac{(p)\mathbf{d}_j - (p)\mathbf{d}_{min}}{(p)\mathbf{d}_{max} - (p)\mathbf{d}_{min}} \\ (p)\mathbf{d}_j &= (p)\hat{\mathbf{d}}_j \cdot (\mathbf{x}_{max} - \mathbf{x}_{min}) + \mathbf{x}_{min} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Once the HSI data has been split into partitions and scaled, the next step consists of the application of the AE model. The proposed AE is composed by 5 layers, as summarized in Table I. These layers are: $l^{(1)}$, the input layer that receives the spectral signature contained in each pixel \mathbf{x}_i of \mathbf{X} (i.e., the rows of the distributed partitions), composed by as many neurons as spectral bands; $l^{(2)}$, $l^{(3)}$ and $l^{(4)}$: the hidden AE-layers, and $l^{(5)}$: the output layer that obtains the reconstructed

signature \mathbf{x}'_i , composed also by as many neurons as spectral bands.

TABLE I
TOPOLOGY OF THE PROPOSED AUTO-ENCODER NEURAL NETWORK FOR
HYPERSPPECTRAL IMAGE ANALYSIS

Layer ID	$l^{(1)}$	$l^{(2)}$	$l^{(3)}$	$l^{(4)}$	$l^{(5)}$
Neurons per $l^{(i)}$	n_{bands}	140	60	140	n_{bands}

With the topology described in Table I in mind, the encoder part is composed by $l^{(1)}$, $l^{(2)}$ and $l^{(3)}$, which performs the mapping from the original spectral space to the latent space of the bottleneck layer $l^{(3)}$. In addition, the decoder part is composed by $l^{(3)}$, $l^{(4)}$ and $l^{(5)}$, which performs the de-mapping from the latent space of $l^{(3)}$ to the original spectral space.

At this point, it is interesting to briefly comment the performance of the AE network. In order to correctly propagate the data through the network, from each partition $(p)\mathbf{D} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{rows} \times (BS \cdot n_{bands})}$, a matrix of unstacked pixels $(p)\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{(BS \cdot n_{rows}) \times n_{bands}}$ is extracted, i.e. the BS spectral pixels that are contained in each $(p)\mathbf{d}_j = [\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_{i+1}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{i+BS}]$ (with $j = 1, \dots, n_{rows}$ and $i = 1, \dots, n_{pixels}$) are each extracted to create, one by one, the rows of $(p)\mathbf{X}$, denoted as $(p)\mathbf{x}_k$ [with $k = 1, \dots, (BS \cdot n_{rows})$] in order to determine the level at which the AE is working.

Every training iteration t is performed using the traditional neural network forward-backward procedure, in addition to a tree-aggregate operation that computes and sums the executors' gradients and losses to return a single loss value and a matrix of gradients. Each executor computes its loss by forwarding the input network data $(p)\mathbf{X}$ through the AE layers, and comparing the $l^{(5)}$ layer's output vector with the vector of input features, following Eq. (4) and obtaining (at each t) the corresponding MSE of the partition: $(p)\text{MSE}_t = E((p)\mathbf{X}, \mathcal{W}_t)$. Gradients are then computed by back-propagating the error signal through the AE, obtaining for each partition the $(p)\mathbf{G}_t$ matrix at iteration t . Each gradient matrix is reduced in the Driver, which runs the optimizer in order to obtain the final matrix $\Delta\mathcal{W}_t$. This matrix indicates how much each neuron weight should be modified before finishing the t -th training iteration, based on how that neuron impacts the output. Fig. 5 gives a graphical overview of the adopted training procedure.

If we denote by P the number of total partitions and by $(p)\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{(BS \cdot n_{rows}) \times n_{bands}}$ the p -th unstacked partition data, composed by $(BS \times n_{rows})$ normalized rows/feature vectors of n_{bands} spectral features, i.e. $(p)\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{bands}} = [{}^{(p)}x_{k,1}, \dots, {}^{(p)}x_{k,n_{bands}}]$, and considering the l -th layer of the AE model, composed by $n_{neurons}^{(l)}$, its output is denoted by $(p)\mathbf{X}^{(l+1)}$ and it is computed by adapting Eq. (1) into Eq. (14) as the matrix multiplication:

$$(p)\mathbf{X}^{(l+1)} = \mathcal{H} \left((p)\mathbf{X}^{(l)} \cdot \mathbf{W}^{(l)} + b^{(l)} \right), \quad (14)$$

where the meaning of each term is:

- $(p)\mathbf{X}^{(l+1)} \in \mathbb{R}^{(BS \times n_{rows}) \times n_{neurons}^{(l)}}$ is the matrix that represents the output of the neurons in layer l with size $(BS \cdot n_{rows}) \times n_{neurons}^{(l)}$, where $n_{neurons}^{(l)}$ is the number

Fig. 5. Distributed forward and backward pipelines of the training stage (at iteration t) after unstacking the hyperspectral pixels in each distributed data partition (each one allocated to a different worker node).

- of neurons of the l -th layer (in the case that $l = 5$, $n_{neurons}^{(5)} = n_{bands}$).
- $(p)\mathbf{X}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{(BS \times n_{rows}) \times n_{neurons}^{(l-1)}}$ is the matrix that serves as input to the l -th layer, which contains the $(BS \cdot n_{rows})$ pixel vectors represented in the feature space of the previous layer, defined by $n_{neurons}^{(l-1)}$ neurons.
- $\mathbf{W}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{neurons}^{(l)} \times n_{neurons}^{(l-1)}}$ is the matrix of weights, which connects the current $n_{neurons}^{(l)}$ neurons with the $n_{neurons}^{(l-1)}$ neurons of the previous layer, and $b^{(l)}$ is the bias of the current layer.
- \mathcal{H} is the ReLU activation function, which gives the following non-linear output: $\text{ReLU}(x) = \max(0, x)$.

After data forwarding, the reconstructed data $(p)\mathbf{X}'$ in the p -th partition at the t -th iteration is compared to the original input $(p)\mathbf{X}$ by applying the MSE function defined by Eq. (4) on each executor. Executors then retrieve the error computed by their carried data, obtaining a value $(p)\text{MSE}_t$ per partition. Then, the final error is obtained as the mean of all executor errors, as shown in Eq. (15):

$$(p)\text{MSE}_t = \frac{1}{(BS \times n_{rows})} \sum_{k=1}^{(BS \times n_{rows})} \|(p)\mathbf{x}_k - (p)\mathbf{x}'_k\|_2$$

$$\text{MSE}_t = \frac{1}{P} \sum_{p=1}^P (p)\text{MSE}_t, \quad (15)$$

where $(BS \times n_{rows})$ is the number of pixels that compose the p -th data partition, whereas $(p)\mathbf{x}_k \in (p)\mathbf{X}$ and $(p)\mathbf{x}'_k \in (p)\mathbf{X}'$ are the original input sample and output reconstructed sample in the p -th data partition, respectively. Those partition errors are then back-propagated to compute the gradient $(p)\mathbf{G}_t$ matrix of each partition at iteration t . In this sense, for each layer in the neural model (using the resulting outputs) the impact that each neuron has on the final error is obtained as the result of the ReLU's derivative of every output, which is defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{H}'(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } x \leq 0 \\ 1, & \text{if } x > 0 \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Such impact can be denoted as $(p)g_t^L = [(p)g_t^{(1)}, \dots, (p)g_t^{(5)}]$, where the l -th element $(p)g_t^{(l)}$ stores the impact of the $n_{neurons}^{(l)}$ allocated into the l -th layer of the network.

The gradient of each partition, $(p)\mathbf{G}_t$, is then computed by applying the *double precision general matrix to matrix multiplication* (DGEMM) operation where, given three input matrices (\mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{C}) and two constants (α and β), the obtained results are calculated by Eq. (17) and stored in \mathbf{C} :

$$\mathbf{C} = \alpha * \mathbf{A} * \mathbf{B} + \beta * \mathbf{C}. \quad (17)$$

DGEMM is performed to compute the entire gradient matrix in parallel, instead of computing each layer gradient vectors separately. This allows us to make neural computations faster and efficient in terms of reducing power consumption. In this sense, each item of Eq. (17) has been replaced by:

- $\alpha = \frac{1}{n_{bands}^{(p)}}$ is a parameter regularizer.
- $\mathbf{A} = (p)\mathbf{X}$ is the input data partition matrix.
- $\mathbf{B} = (p)g_t^L$ is the matrix representing the impact of each neuron on every layer of the neural network.
- $\beta = 1$ is also a parameter regularizer. As \mathbf{C} should be unchanged, it has been set to 1.
- $\mathbf{C} = (p)\mathbf{G}_{t-1}$ is initially the older gradient matrix of the p -th partition. After the updates resulting from the DGEMM operation, the current gradient $(p)\mathbf{G}_t$ is stored on \mathbf{C} .

Finally, the gradient matrix G_t of the whole network is computed as the average of the sum of all partition's gradients: $(p)\mathbf{G}_t$. The entire training process on each data partition is graphically illustrated on Fig. 5.

The final optimization step is performed locally on the master node using a variant of the BFGS algorithm, called limited BFGS (L-BFGS). Since BFGS needs a huge amount of memory for the computation of the matrices, L-BFGS limits the memory usage, so it fits better into our implementation. The optimizer uses the computed gradients and a step-size procedure to get closer to a minimum of Eq. (4). The procedure is repeated until a desired number of iterations, $n_{iterations}$, is reached.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

A. Configuration of the Environment

In order to test our newly developed implementation, a dedicated hardware and software environment based on a high-end cloud computing paradigm has been adopted. The virtual resources have been provided by the JetStream Cloud Services³ at the Indiana University Pervasive Technology Institute (PTI) through XSEDE allocation TG-ASC180012 [64], [65], [66]. Its user interface is based on Atmosphere computing platform⁴ and uses Openstack⁵ as the operational software environment.

The hardware environment consists of a collection of cloud computing nodes. In particular, the cluster consists of one master node and eight slave nodes, which are hosted in virtual machines with six virtual cores at 2.5 GHz each. Every node has 16 GB of RAM and 60 GB of storage via a Block Storage File System. As mentioned before, Spark performs as the backbone for node interconnection, meanwhile data transfers are supported by a local 4x40 Gbps dedicated network.

Each virtual machine runs Ubuntu 16.04 as operating system, with Spark 2.1.1 and Java 1.8 serving as running platforms. The Spark framework provides a distributed machine learning library known as Spark Machine Learning Library (MLlib⁶), which is used as support for the implementation of our distributed AE network for remotely sensed HSI data analysis. Moreover, the proposed implementation has been coded in Scala 2.11, compiled into Java bytecode and interpreted in JVMs. Finally, mathematical operations from MLlib are handled by Breeze (the numerical processing library for Scala), in its 0.12 version, and by Netlib 1.1.2. In this sense, Netlib wraps JVM calls into low level Basic Linear Algebra Subprograms (BLAS) calls, so those calls are executed faster than traditional executions.

B. Hyperspectral Datasets

With the aim of testing the performance of our newly developed cloud-based and distributed AE network model, two different HSI data sets have been considered in our experiments. These data sets correspond to the full version of the AVIRIS Indian Pines scene, referred hereinafter as the big Indian Pines scene (BIP), and a set of images corresponding to six different zones captured by the Hyperion spectrometer [67] onboard NASA's EO-1 Satellite, which we have designated as Hyperion data set (HYPERION). Both data sets are characterized by their huge size, which makes them ideal to be processed in a cloud-distributed environment. In the following, we provide a description of the aforementioned data sets.

- The **big Indian Pines** scene (BIP) scene (see Fig. 6) was collected by AVIRIS in 1992 [5] over agricultural fields in northwestern Indiana. The image comprises a full flightline with a total of 2678×614 pixels (with 20 meters per pixel spatial resolution), covering 220 spectral bands from 400 to 2500 nm.

- The **Hyperion data set** (HYPERION) is composed by six full flightlines (see Fig. 7) collected in 2016 by the Hyperion spectrometer mounted on NASA's EO-1 satellite, which collects spectral signatures using 220 spectral channels ranging from 357 to 2576 nm with 10-nm bandwidth. The captured scenes have a spatial resolution of 30 meters per pixel. The standard scene width and length are 7.7 km and 42 km, respectively, with an optional increased scene length of 185 km. In particular, the considered images have been stacked and treated together as a single image comprising 20401×256 pixels with the spectral range mentioned above. These images have been provided by the Earth Resources Observation and Science (EROS) Center in GEOTIFF format⁷. Also, each scene is accompanied by one identifier in the format *YDDDXXXML*, which indicates the day of acquisition (*DDD*), and the sensor that recorded the image (*XXX*, denoting Hyperion, ALI or AC with 0=off and 1=on), the pointing mode (*M*, which can be *N* for Nadir, *P* for Pointed within path/row or *K* for Pointed outside path/row) and the scene length (*L*, which can be *F* for Full scene, *P* for Partial scene, *Q* for Second partial scene and *S* for Swath). Also, other letters can be used to create distinct entity IDs, for example to indicate the Ground/Receiving Station (*GGG*) or the Version Number (*VV*). In this case, the identifiers of the six considered images are: 065110KU, 035110KU, 212110KR, 247110KW, 261110KR and 321110KR.

C. Experiments and Discussion

Four different experiments have been conducted in order to validate the performance of our cloud-distributed AE for HSI data compression:

- 1) The first experiment analyzes the scalability of our cloud-distributed AE, using a medium-sized data set. For this purpose, the BIP data set has been processed with a fixed number of training samples in the cloud environment described above, using one master and different numbers of worker nodes. Here, we have reduced the dimensionality of the BIP data set using the implemented cloud AE model to obtain a reduced data representation with 60 spectral channels.
- 2) The second experiment illustrates the internal parallelization (at the core level) of the worker nodes. Our main goal is to show that, using a fixed amount of workers and increasing only the data volumes, speedups grow linearly, as well as the computing times. For this purpose, the HYPERION data set has been processed using four different percentages of training data and 8 worker nodes in the considered cluster, each with 6 virtual cores. As in the previous experiment, we reduced the dimensionality of the HYPERION data set using the implemented cloud AE network, extracting 60 spectral channels.

³<https://jetstream-cloud.org/>

⁴<https://www.atmosphereiot.com/platform.html>

⁵<https://www.openstack.org/>

⁶<https://spark.apache.org/mllib>

⁷These scenes are available online from the Earth Explorer site, <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov>

Fig. 6. False RGB color map of the big Indian Pines (BIP) scene, represented using the visualization method in [47]

Fig. 7. False RGB color map of the Hyperion data set (HYPERION), represented using the visualization method in [47]

- 3) The third experiment tests the performance of our cloud-distributed AE using different numbers of training samples and worker nodes over a large data set, to illustrate how efficiency grows with the number of workers. This experiment allows us to understand the internal operation of data partitions. In this sense, the HYPERION data set used in the previous experiment has been considered again using 4 different training percentages and 6 different numbers of worker nodes.
- 4) The fourth experiment compares the compression performance of our considered autoencoder implementations (using different activation functions: linear and ReLU) versus the compression performance of a state-of-the-art method such as PCA. In this experiment, we use a subset of the big Indian Pines data that has been widely used in the hyperspectral imaging community, with 145×145

pixels and 200 spectral bands.

At this point, it is important to emphasize that the experiments above have been performed by running 400 training iterations, with the BS set to 256. Also, in order to evaluate the performance of the proposed cloud method, the mean square error (MSE), the mean absolute error (MAE), and the spectral angle distance (SAD) metrics have been considered.

1) *Experiment 1:* Our first experiment evaluates the performance of the distributed implementation of the proposed AE, using the BIP scene, reduced to 60 spectral channels. In this case the network employs 80% of randomly selected samples to create the training set and the remaining 20% of the samples to create the test set. In order to demonstrate the scalability of our cloud-distributed AE, the cloud environment has been configured with one master node and different numbers of worker nodes, specifically: 1, 2, 4, 8, 12 and 16 workers. In

TABLE II
AVERAGE RUNTIME AND SPEEDUP WITH THE PROCESSING TIMES AND SPEEDUPS OBTAINED FOR DIFFERENT NUMBERS OF WORKERS WHEN PROCESSING THE BIP IMAGE.

BIP	Training percentage (size)	Number of workers					
		1	2	4	8	12	16
Time (s)	80 (2760 MB)	17398.74	8991.12	4518.39	2354.91	1803.27	1288.69
Speedup	80 (2760 MB)	1	1.9308	3.8506	7.3882	9.6484	13.5011

Fig. 8. Comparison between the original (in blue) and reconstructed (in dotted red) spectral signatures extracted from the BIP scene by the proposed cloud AE implementation using 8 workers.

TABLE III
PERFORMANCE EVALUATION USING THE BIG AND HYPERION DATASETS (THE FIRST ONE WITH A FIXED NUMBER OF TRAINING SAMPLES AND DIFFERENT NUMBERS OF WORKER NODES, AND THE SECOND ONE WITH DIFFERENT NUMBERS OF TRAINING SAMPLES AND WORKER NODES).

	Training percentage (size)	Implementations		
		Parallel version	Cloud version	
BIP	MSE	1.461e-4	1.590e-4	
	MAE	7.812e-3	8.373e-4	
	SAD	5.489e-2	5.816e-4	
HYPERION	Implementations			
	Training percentage (size)		Parallel version	Cloud version
	MSE	20 (1838 MB)	1.05e-4	1.23e-4
		40 (3676 MB)	8.01e-5	1.24e-4
		60 (5515 MB)	6.79e-5	1.26e-4
		80 (7353 MB)	N/A	1.27e-4
	MAE	20 (1838 MB)	5.58e-3	6.18e-3
		40 (3676 MB)	4.73e-3	6.21e-3
		60 (5515 MB)	3.60e-3	6.07e-3
		80 (7353 MB)	N/A	6.36e-3
	SAD	20 (1838 MB)	11.97e-2	11.8e-2
		40 (3676 MB)	11.63e-2	11.7e-2
60 (5515 MB)		12.01e-2	11.9e-2	
80 (7353 MB)		N/A	12.0e-2	

order to show the robustness of our model, five Monte Carlo runs have been executed, obtaining as a result the average and the standard deviation of those executions.

Fig. 9 shows the obtained speed-up in a graphical way. Such speed-up has been calculated as T_1/T_n , where T_1 is the execution time of the slowest execution with one worker node and T_n is the average time of the executions with n worker nodes. Comparing the theoretical and real speed-up values obtained, it can be observed that the model is able to scale very well, reaching a speed-up value that is very close to the theoretical one with 2, 4 and 8 workers. However, for 12 workers and beyond, we can see that the communication times between the nodes hamper the speed-up due to the insufficient amount of data, a fairly common behaviour in cloud environments, in which the main bottleneck

Fig. 9. Scalability of the proposed cloud-distributed network when processing the BIP dataset with 1, 2, 4, 8, 12 and 16 worker nodes and 1 master node. The red line indicates the theoretical speed-up value and the blue bars indicate the actual values reached.

occurs in the communication between nodes. As a result, it is important to make sure that there exists an adequate balance between the total amount of data to be processed and the number of processing nodes. Tables II and III tabulate the performance data collected in this experiment, coupled with the reconstruction errors, computation times and speed-ups, respectively. In particular, Table III compares the obtained results with a parallel version of the same AE architecture using a standard DL-framework (Torch). As we can observe, the proposed cloud methodology is able to obtain a similar MSE than a traditional DL-framework, however both the MAE and the SAD measurements are significantly smaller (in particular the SAD), demonstrating that the proposed implementation is able to improve the performance of a current DL-framework. Also, Fig. 10 shows the evolution of the training loss of the proposed method compared with the one exhibited by the Torch implementation. As we can see in Fig.

Fig. 10. Training loss evolution of the proposed cloud AE compared with a parallel version implemented with the Torch DL-framework on the BIG dataset during (a) the first 20 epochs, the first 80 epochs (b), and the first 200 epochs (c).

10(a), the proposed implementation is more stable than the parallel version, being able to reduce the loss faster than the Torch implementation, until both lines converge on Fig. 10(c), being the train loss of the proposed method slightly lower.

These very low errors are finally reflected in Fig. 8, which shows three reconstructed signatures of different materials in the BIP scene. As it can be seen in Fig. 8, the reconstructed signatures are extremely similar to the original ones, a fact that allows for their exploitation in advanced processing tasks such as classification or spectral unmixing.

2) *Experiment 2*: Our second experiment explores the internal parallelization of each worker node (at the core level) in order to illustrate that computation and communication times grow in a similar (linear) way. For this purpose, the cloud-distributed AE has been tested on the HYPERION dataset, again reducing the spectral dimensionality to 60 spectral bands and randomly collecting 20%, 40%, 60% and 80% of training samples to create the training set, and the remaining 80%, 60%, 40% and 20% to create the test set. Moreover, 1 master node and 8 worker nodes (each one with 6 virtual cores) have been considered to implement the cloud environment.

Fig. 11(a) shows the results obtained in this experiment. If we compare the theoretical speed-up values and the real ones obtained, it can be seen that our implementation is able to reach a speed-up that is almost identical to the theoretical one. This is quite important, as the obtained results indicate that the scalability achieved in each node (in terms of computing time) is almost linear with regards to the size of the HSI scenes considered in each node, thanks to the cores available in each node. In this way, the proposed cloud-distributed AE implementation takes full advantage of all the available resources, both in parallel (multi-core) and distributed fashion.

3) *Experiment 3*: Our third experiment evaluates how the performance of the proposed cloud AE for HSI data compression is affected by the number of workers available in the cloud environment and the amount of training data using a very large-sized data set. The HYPERION images have been considered for this purpose. Due to the great amount of data, this experiment has been split in two parts. The first part performs a comparison over a cloud environment composed by 1, 2, 4, 8, 12 and 16 worker nodes, and 1 master node, employing the 20% and 40% of the samples to create the

training set, and the remaining 80% and 60% of data to create the test set. However, due to the memory limitations of the workers, the second part performs a comparison over a cloud environment composed by 2, 4, 8, 12 and 16 worker nodes, and 1 master node, employing the 60% and 80% of the samples to create the training set, and the remaining 40% and 20% of data to create the test set. In this context, it must be noted that while in the first part the speed-up is obtained based on the implementation with 1 worker node, in the second one the speed-up is obtained based on the implementation with 2 worker nodes.

Figs. 11(b) and 11(c) show the results obtained by the two parts of this experiment in a graphical way. In this case, it is interesting to observe that the theoretical speed-up and the linear speed-up values do not coincide. When we talk about linear speed-up, we normally refer to the expected speed-up when linear partitioning is performed in the cluster. However, in a real environment the partitioning is not always linear. In fact, we can observe a performance gap in the 8-node configuration. This can be explained by the relationship between the total number of cores in the cluster, C (obtained as the number of cores per node multiplied by the number of nodes), and the number of existing data partitions, P , given by Eq. (18):

$$(\lambda - 1) \cdot C < P < \lambda \cdot C, \quad (18)$$

where λ is a scalar. For instance, when using 8-node configuration, its value is set to $\lambda = 2$. Taking Eq. (18) into consideration, and assuming that the cluster cores execute tasks when they are free, the non-compliance of Eq. (18) leads to the fact that some cores remain idle after finishing their first allocated tasks, so the fine-grained parallelism is not fully exploited in this case.

In the considered cluster, since each node has 6 cores, a total of $C = 6 \times N$ working cores can be exploited. Furthermore, these C working cores allow for the processing of the data partitions in batches of C tasks at most. For instance, when a configuration of 8 nodes is used, the cluster environment is made up of a total of $C = 6 \times 8 = 48$ working cores. This indicates that, at most, in one processing batch Spark will launch 48 tasks. As Spark splits the HSD data on 58 data partitions, 58 tasks must be executed over each partition.

Fig. 11. Scalability of the proposed cloud-distributed network when processing the HYPERION data set in experiments 2 and 3: a) with 8 worker nodes and 1 master node, considering 20%, 40%, 60% and 80% of training data (experiment 2), b) with 1, 2, 4, 8, 12 and 16 worker nodes and 1 master node, considering 20% and 40% of training data (experiment 3, first part), and c) with 2, 4, 8, 12 and 16 worker nodes and 1 master node, considering 60% and 80% of training data (experiment 3, second part). The numbers in the parentheses indicate the total amount of data used in MB. The red lines indicates the theoretical speed-up value (red-continuous line) and linear speed-up value (red-dotted line), while the blue and orange bars indicate the actual values reached.

TABLE IV

AVERAGE RUNTIME AND SPEEDUP WITH THE PROCESSING TIMES AND SPEEDUPS OBTAINED FOR DIFFERENT NUMBERS OF WORKERS AND DIFFERENT AMOUNTS OF TRAINING DATA WHEN PROCESSING THE HYPERION DATASET.

		Training percentage (size)	Number of workers					
			1	2	4	8	12	16
HYPERION	Time (s)	20 (1838 MB)	14919.73	7632.64	4433.11	2952.27	1606.94	1171.87
		40 (3676 MB)	30526.79	15709.24	9087.66	5721.97	3311.36	2182.60
		60 (5515 MB)	N/A	21505.27	12458.54	8456.84	4536.73	3122.92
		80 (7353 MB)	N/A	32645.44	18900.49	11633.75	6084.69	4103.02
	Speedup	20 (1838 MB)	1	1.9547	3.3655	5.0536	9.2845	12.7315
		40 (3676 MB)	1	1.9432	3.3591	5.2796	9.2187	13.9864
		60 (5515 MB)	N/A	1	1.7247	2.5191	4.7402	6.8862
		80 (7353 MB)	N/A	1	1.7268	2.8304	5.3651	7.9564

However, in each batch only 48 tasks can be performed. This means that two batches must be run; the first one with 48 tasks and the second one with only 10. As a result, the second batch cannot fully exploit fine-grained parallelism as only 10 cores are being used, with 38 idle nodes. This results in an unnecessary waste of computing resources.

However, when the idle cores from the second batch are used, the performance improves. This is the case of the 12-node configuration ($C = 72$), where the partitioning becomes more efficient, complying with Eq. (18). Linear speed-up based on workers needs to be added to this core-level speed-up, leading to a new speed-up which is calculated as the multiplication of those speed-ups, as indicated by Eq. (19):

$$\frac{T_1^w}{T_n^w} \cdot \frac{T_1^p}{T_n^p}, \quad (19)$$

where T_n^w is the processing time at the *worker* level and T_n^p the processing time at the *core* level.

With the aforementioned observations in mind, and focusing on the results given by the first part of the experiment and reported on Fig. 11(b) we can observe that, for each configuration and training with 20% and 40% of the available samples, the proposed AE exhibits quite similar speed-ups, with slight variations due to the distribution of data and the role of idle nodes. It is interesting to observe with 1-8 nodes how the speed-up is quite similar to the theoretical one, while with 12-16 nodes the differences between obtained and theoretical

speed-up values are higher, indicating that the proposed AE with only 20% and 40% of training samples does not take full advantage of the cloud environment's potential.

On the other part, Fig. 11(c) reports the obtained results of the second part of this experiment. In this case, the base implementation of the AE is conducted on a cloud environment with 2 worker nodes, employing 60% and 80% of training data. With 2 and 4 worker nodes the obtained speed-up values are very similar employing 60% and 80% of the available samples, while with 8, 12 and 16 nodes it is clear how the version with more training data is able to achieve a superior speed-up, reaching a value very similar to the theoretical one with 16 nodes. This indicates that the amount of data handled in this case is more convenient to take full advantage of the way that Spark organizes data partitions and tasks in batches, achieving better parallelization at the core level (fine-grained parallelism) and also better distribution at the worker level (coarse-grained parallelism). These conclusions are supported by the data tabulated in Table IV where the speed-up employing 20% and 40% of training data has been obtained taking as base times the cloud environment with 1 node, while for 60% and 80% of training data the speed-up is obtained comparing with the environment composed by 2 worker nodes due to the exhausting use of memory. Regarding the compression performance, Table III compares the MSE, MAE and SAD obtained by the proposed version and

Fig. 12. Obtained compression metrics: MSE (a), SAD (b), and MAE (c) for different bottleneck sizes, after using PCA and the proposed autoencoder implementation with different activation functions: linear and non-linear (ReLU). In all cases, we train the models using 75% of the AVIRIS Indian Pines image, which is actually a subset of the big Indian Pines image (composed by 145×145 pixels with 200 bands).

a standard implementation using the DL-framework Torch. In this case, the MSE is slightly worse than the parallel version, while the MAE and SAD are quite similar. It is interesting to observe that the considered measures keep constant with different amounts of training data, which indicates that the network is able to optimize very well, without overfitting the parameters when 60% or 80% of the available training samples are used, but also avoiding underfitting when few samples are used for training purposes.

4) *Experiment 4:* In order to evaluate the compression performance against another state-of-art method, a comparison between the proposed autoencoder implementation and the well-known PCA is given in Fig. 12. Specifically, this experiment reports three different compression metrics (MSE, MAE and SAD) obtained (for different bottleneck sizes) using the PCA algorithm, the linear autoencoder, and the non-linear autoencoder (ReLU). This experiment has been carried out by training the considered methods with 75% of the small AVIRIS Indian Pines dataset (a subset of the big Indian Pines image with size of 145×145 pixels and 200 spectral bands). In this sense, with the aim of providing a fair and in-depth comparison between PCA and the proposed neural-inspired models, we have scaled the input data, introducing batch normalization to the models' layers in order to center the data, as the considered implementation of PCA standardizes the data before the singular vector decomposition (SVD, employing LAPACK solver). Moreover the considered bottleneck sizes are in the range from 1 to 32, with steps of 2^n and $n = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$. As we can clearly see in Fig. 12, when reducing the number of dimensions our proposed implementation (with a linear activation function) performs as well as PCA. However, our proposed implementation (with non-linear activation function) clearly outperforms PCA. This is due to the fact that the ReLU-based autoencoder is able to find non-linear relationships in the data, which assists in the task of reducing the dimensionality of such data and provides a more effective dimensionality reduction strategy than linear methods such as PCA, whose performance clearly decays as we attempt to reduce the data to a small number of dimensions. In this case, the PCA (as a linear method) is not able to find such non-linear correlations between variables. It is also remarkable

that, as the target dimensionality grows, the difference between both methods tends to be smaller. From this experiment, we can conclude that the small error obtained with the non-linear autoencoder when reducing the data into a small number of dimensions makes it a highly desirable alternative against linear solutions such as PCA, as it is able to represent the input data better than PCA in a reduced dimension space.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE LINES

This paper presents a new cloud-based AE neural network for remotely sensed HSI data analysis in distributed fashion. This kind of artificial neural network finds non-linear solutions when compressing the data, as opposed to traditional techniques such as PCA. In this sense, the proposed approach is more suitable for complex data sets such as HSIs. The proposed AE implementation over a Spark cluster exhibits great performance, not only in terms of data compression and error reconstruction, but also in terms of scalability when processing huge data volumes, which cannot be achieved by traditional (sequential) AE implementations. Those sequential algorithms may be a valid option when the data to be managed and analyzed can be stored in a single machine with limited processing and memory resources. However, for large amounts of HSI data, sequential implementations can easily run out of memory or require a vast amount of computing time, which cannot be assumed when reliable processing is needed in a reasonable time. In this regard, both HPC and HTC alternatives have provided new paths to solve those problems, including parallelization on GPUs and distribution/parallelization on clusters with cloud computing-based solutions. The experiments carried out in this work demonstrate that cloud versions of HSI data processing methods provide efficient and effective HPC-HTC alternatives that successfully solve the inherent problems of sequential versions by increasing hardware capabilities in a cheaper way as compared with other solutions such as grid computing. Also, the obtained results reveal that the computation performance of cloud-based solutions easily increases with larger data sets, taking advantage of the computational load distribution when there is a good balance between the amount of data and the cluster complexity. Encouraged by the good results obtained in this

work, in the future we will develop other implementation of HSI processing techniques in cloud computing environments. Further work will also explore the design of more sophisticated scheduling algorithms in order to circumvent the negative impact introduced by idle processing cores in our current implementation.

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